

The Role of Cryptographic Techniques in Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) Systems

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Abstract— This review is about the key role of cryptographic techniques in fortifying Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) systems in the automotive sector. In 2020, the FBI reported 810,400 vehicles stolen, and RKE attacks are playing a critical role in those [1]. This paper reviews various cryptographic mechanisms used in RKE systems and their importance in maintaining the security and integrity of vehicular access controls. Robust cryptographic measures are essential to counter unauthorized access and prevalent attacks such as Replay and Roll Jam attacks [2]. However, continual research is essential to address evolving security challenges.

Keywords—Remote Keyless Entry (RKE), Cryptography, Vehicular Security, Attacks on RKE, Rolling Codes, Replay Attacks.

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

The automotive industry is experiencing a rapid evolution driven by the increasing connectivity of vehicles [3]. Today's vehicles, often called "computers on wheels," are equipped with many electrical and electronic systems, including keyless entry systems, which have evolved significantly over the years [4]. Figure 1 illustrates the potential entry points for vehicle hacking. Key and entry system is one of those [5] [6].

Figure 1 potential entry points on a vehicle for cyber criminals

Evolution of Keys and Entry Systems

For decades after the invention of the automobile vehicles had no keys. The first key, introduced by Chrysler Corporation in 1949, was an ignition tool and a safety measure to prevent unintended vehicle movement. The evolution continued with the introduction of immobilizers pioneered by Honda. These keys embedded RFID technology near the keyhole, and its effectiveness was proven by reducing car theft rates. Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) systems marked the next milestone, enabling users to lock or unlock their vehicles from the key fob. RKE systems rely on Radio Frequency (RF) signals for communication, with varying frequency bands based on geographic location.

This paper focuses exclusively on Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) systems, exploring their cryptographic mechanisms and methods to ensure vehicular security within the evolving automotive landscape [7] [8].

II. REVIEW LITERATURE

A. Remote Keyless Entry

Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) systems have become common in most vehicles. These systems revolutionize vehicle access by allowing users to interact with their cars remotely, offering convenience and enhanced security. To understand the importance of RKE technology, figure 2 and the following illustrate how it works and how it functions:

- **User-Initiated Activation:** When a user presses a button on the key fob, it triggers the central processing unit (CPU) within it.
- **Radio Frequency Transmission:** The CPU generates a data stream and then transmits it as a radio signal through an antenna facilitated by a radio frequency transmitter.
- **Vehicle Reception:** On the vehicle's side, a receiver captures this radio signal and forwards it to its CPU.
- **Decoding and Command Execution:** The vehicle's CPU deciphers the received data and executes the relevant commands via the command module.

RKE systems typically comprise three components as, a transmitter, a receiver, and an antenna [9] [10]. The transmitter encodes data into radio signals, the antenna facilitates

Figure 2 Block diagram for remote keyless

signal transmission and reception, and the receiver decodes and filters the incoming signals, ensuring their compatibility with the intended system. RKE systems have a key fob and a device. When the key fob is pressed, it initiates the transmission of a radio frequency signal to the device, carrying an instruction command for execution. These systems are used in tasks such as RKE in vehicles, opening garage doors, and controlling various car features [11] [12].

Cryptographic Techniques in RKE Systems

Heart of the Modern Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) systems are the cryptographic techniques that are used to secure vehicular access. These techniques mitigate unauthorized access and prevent attacks, such as Replay and RollJam attacks, in the automotive landscape [9].

Symmetric Cryptography in RKE Systems

Symmetric cryptography, also known as secret-key cryptography, is the primary cryptographic technique used in RKE systems. It encrypts all communication between the key fob and the vehicle, ensuring the confidentiality of data transmitted over the air. Symmetric cryptography implements mutual authentication protocols, verifying the legitimacy of the key fob and the vehicle's CPU before exchanging sensitive data [13] [14] [15].

a) Efficiency, Speed and authentication

Symmetric encryption algorithms are efficient and well-suited for real-time communication in RKE systems. Symmetric algorithms are speed, and it is essential in RKE systems, where users expect the locking and unlocking process to be swift and seamless [16].

b) Confidentiality and Key Management

Symmetric encryption ensures the confidentiality of data transmitted between the key fob and the vehicle by encrypting all data with a shared secret key. Only the key fob and the vehicle, which have the shared secret key it shared by Asymmetric algorithms, and it can decrypt the data. It prevents attackers from eavesdropping on the communication and stealing sensitive data [13].

2) Asymmetric Cryptography

Asymmetric cryptography can also establish a secure channel between the key fobs. The problem is the efficiency, but Asymmetric Cryptography is very useful for doing other tasks like [17]:

Key distribution

Key distribution is the process of securely exchanging the shared secret key between the key fob and the vehicle. It can be challenging to achieve, especially if the key fob and vehicle are not physically close to each other. Asymmetric cryptography can solve this problem by generating a public/private key pair on the vehicle, and then the public key transmits to the key fob. The key fob can then use the public key to encrypt the shared secret key and transmit it to the vehicle. The vehicle can then decrypt the shared secret key using its private key. This key distribution method is secure; the private key never transmits to the key fob, and even if an attacker intercepts, they cannot decrypt the shared secret key [13] [17].

Digital signatures

A digital signature is an asymmetric cryptographic technique to verify data's authenticity and integrity. The sender uses their private key to sign the message to create a digital signature. It creates a unique digital signature that is attached to the message. The recipient can verify the digital signature with the sender's public key. If the signature is valid, it proves that the legitimate sender sent the message and has not been tampered with in transit. Digital signatures can prevent replay attacks and man-in-the-middle attacks in RKE systems. In modern automotive RKE systems, the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is the popular symmetric encryption algorithm. AES, ideal for its security

and efficiency, is widely adopted in RKE. The most used Asymmetric algorithm is RSA. The elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) algorithm and Diffie-Hellman key exchange are also used [18] [13]. Figure 3 illustrates the real example of the process of the key fob to the vehicle's Body Control Module (BCM) pairing steps in Tesla X [19].

Figure 3 process of the key fob to the BCM pairing “We use || to denote the concatenation operation. pk_{Sx} and sk_{Sy} denote the RSA public key from slot x and the RSA private key from slot y respectively.”

RKE technologies and attacks

A. Replay attacks and fixed code.

In early Remote Keyless Entry (RKE) systems, a vulnerable mechanism called "fixed codes" was used, where each car had a unique authentication code [20]. When a user used the key fob, this code was sent along with a command code to execute actions. However, this system had a critical vulnerability to replay attacks. Replay attacks involve intercepting the radio signal transmitted by the key fob and replaying it to gain unauthorized access to the vehicle [21]. These attacks were relatively easy to execute and required no expensive hardware. Honda and Acura models had replay attack vulnerability (CVE-2019-20626) in 2020 [22]. According to the Global Automotive Cybersecurity Report 2021, 95% of the tested vehicles are vulnerable to Replay attacks [23]. Figure 4 shows a fixed code replay attack [20] [24].

Figure 4 Fixed code replay attack

B. Rolling Codes

Unlike older fixed code systems, rolling code systems generate a different code each time the key fob is pressed. This approach enhances security. In rolling code systems, both the key fob and the vehicle maintain a list of valid codes. Each time a signal is sent or received, a counter is updated, and a pseudo-random number generator (PRNG) algorithm is used to generate the next code based on the counter and a shared cryptographic key. This constant code change makes it extremely difficult for attackers to intercept and replay signals [20] [25].

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